

CAP Conditionality for agroforestry systems

- Agroforestry aligns some GAEC compulsory requirements promoted by the EU such as establishment of buffer strips along water courses and non productive areas of features in agricultural areas as they are usually woody perennials
- Agroforestry contributes to the main GAEC goals linked to climate and environment, public and plant health as well as animal welfare
- Agroforestry fulfils the compulsory requirements linked to the SMR

GAEC and SMR CAP goals

EU farmers must compulsory fulfill the GAEC (standards for the Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions of land) and the SMR (Statutory Management Requirement) to receive CAP funds. The GAEC goals are linked to biodiversity protection and enhancement on the one hand and water and habitat protection on the other. Moreover, agroforestry is able to contribute to the objectives of food safety, plant protection and animal protection by further contribute to the SMR goals.

Agroforestry linked to GAEC biodiversity goals

BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION

- GAEC#1.** Maintain a certain share of permanent grassland of the total agricultural area
- GAEC#2.** Protect wetlands and peatlands
- GAEC#3.** Maintain soil organic matter and soil structure through a ban of burning arable stubble
- GAEC#5.** Prevent soil erosion through relevant practices
- GAEC#6.** protect soil by defining rules for minimum soil cover
- GAEC#9.** protect environmentally-sensitive permanent grasslands in Natura 2000 sites

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BIODIVERSITY ENHANCEMENT

- GAEC#4.** Protect water from pollution through the establishment of buffer strips along water courses
- GAEC#7.** preserve the soil potential through crop rotation
- GAEC#8.** maintain non-productive areas and landscape features, and ensure the retention of landscape features

FIGURE 2. Olive grove with damaged soil due to water erosion in Jaén, Andalucía, Spain. Couso, A.

AF4EU: a groundbreaking initiative to foster European agroforestry

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